

2-TUR QANDLI DIABET XAMDA SURUNKALI YURAK YETISHMOVCHILIGI BILAN XASTALANGAN BEMORLARDA BIOMARKYORLARNI ANIQLASHNING KLINIK AXAMIYATI

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Annotatsiya: Hozirgi vaqtda iqtisodiy rivojlangan mamlakatlarda ikkita tibbiy va ijtimoiy muammo juda dolzarb: o'limning boshqa sabablari orasida yetakchi o'rinni egallagan yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari va qandli diabet (QD). Surunkali yurak etishmovchiligi (SYuYe) ko'plab yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining natijasi bo'lib, progressiv kurs va o'ta noqulay prognoz bilan tavsiflanadi. Ma'lumki, SYuYe rivojlanishining mustaqil xavf omili diabetdir. Shu munosabat bilan, 2-toifa diabet bilan bog'liq bo'lgan yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari (YuQTK) bo'lgan bemorlarda yurak-qon tomir asoratlari rivojlanish xavfini erta tashxislashning yangi usullarini ishlab chiqish ayniqsa dolzarbdir.

Kalit so'zlar: qandli diabet , surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi , glukoza , tana vazn indeksi

Abstract: Currently, two medical and social problems are very urgent in economically developed countries: cardiovascular diseases and diabetes mellitus, which are the leading causes of death among other causes. Chronic heart failure (CHF) is the result of many cardiovascular diseases and is characterized by a progressive course and an extremely unfavorable prognosis. It is known that an independent risk factor for the development of CHF is diabetes. In this regard, with type 2 diabetes The development of new methods for early diagnosis of the risk of developing cardiovascular complications in patients with associated cardiovascular diseases (CVD) is especially relevant.

Key words: diabetes mellitusn, chronic heart failure , glucose , body weight index

Muammoning dolzarbligi.

Ma'lumki, 2-tur diabet bilan ogrigan bemorlarning 60% dan ortigida yurak ishemik kasalligining erta rivojlanishi tufayli umr ko'rish davomiyligi qisqaradi. Surunkali yurak etishmovchiligi (SYuYe) yurak-qon tomir tizimi kasalliklarining eng keng tarqalgan, og'ir va prognostik jixatdan xavfli asoratidir. Bundan tashqari, chap qorincha disfunktsiyasi bo'lgan bemorlarning ko'p soni mavjud bo'lib, ular ba'zi ma'lumotlarga ko'ra, u 12% ga yaqin (taxminan 16 million kishi). Rossiyada SYuEni davolash uchun xar yili 55 dan 295 milliard rublgacha sarflanadi va SYuYe bilan ogrigan bemorlarning axvoli yomonlashgani sababli kasalxonaga yotqizish narxi 184,7 milliard rublga yetadi. Shunday qilib, bu muammo nafaqat tibbiy, balki ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy xususiyatga ega.

Tadqiqot maqsadi. 2-tur kandli diabet bilan kasallangan bemorlarda miokardning klinik va funksional xolatini tavsiflovchi markyorlarni aniqlash.

Tadqiqot vazifalari:

1. Qandli diabet 2-tur va surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi bilan xastalangan bemorlarda klinik-metabolik baholash xarakteristikasi
2. Qandli diabet 2-tur va surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi bilan xastalangan bemorlarda biomarkerlar diagnostik qiymati, NT pro BNP qiymatini aniqlash.
3. Qandli diabet 2-tur va surunkali yurak yetishmovchiligi bilan xastalangan bemorlarda yurakning qon otib berish xajmiga bog'liq ravishda XOMA indeks va insulinga rezistentlikni baxolash.

Olingan natijalar

Glikemik nazorat zamonaviy diabetni davolashning asosidir. Qon tomir devorida aterosklerotik jarayonning shakllanishida surunkali giperglikemiyaning toksik roli qisman qon tomir endoteliyasining umumiy disfunktsiyasining rivojlanishi, oksidlovchi stressning kuchayishi va diabetik lipidlarning buzilishi, shuningdek kardiomiotsitlarga yurak o'tkazuvchanligi va yurakning kichik tomirlaridagi o'zgarishlar bevosita ta'sir qilish natijasida amalga oshiriladi. Giperglikemiya qon tomir devorining ateromatoz lezyonlarining birlamchi o'choqlari paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi va ateromalarning o'ziga xos hujayrali komponentini shakllantirish uchun sharoit yaratadi. Natijada, giperglikemiya aterosklerotik plaklarning shakllanishiga olib keladi, ularning hujayrali va interstitsial tuzilishi ularning tolali kapsulasida yorilish paydo bo'lishiga yordam beradi. Bu o'z navbatida, aterosklerotik blyashka o'sishining dastlabki bosqichlarida koronar

tomirlarning aniq obliteratsiyalangan shikastlanishlari bo'lmaganda, YuIK erta va og'ir asoratlarini rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Bu to'satdan yurak-qon tomir o'limini yoki o'tkir koronar sindromning (O'KS) klinik ko'rinishini keltirib chiqaradigan intrakoronar tromboz shakllanishi bilan blyashka yorilishi va qon ketishi yuzaga keladi. Blyashkalarining asemptomatik yorilishi, yorilish joyidan pastda mikrotomirlarning tiqilib qolishi natijasida qon aylanish yetishmovchiligining tez rivojlanishiga olib keladi. 2-tur diabet bilan og'rigan bemorlarda bunday yorilishlar diabetsiz odamlarga qaraganda deyarli 3 baravar tez-tez uchraydi

Xulosalar

1. Ochlikdagi glyukoza darajasidan qat'i nazar, yuqori postprandial giperglikemiya o'lim xavfi 1,7-2,25 baravar yuqori edi. Ushbu ma'lumotlar shuni ko'rsatadiki, 2-tur diabetda YuQTB hodisalari xavfini baholashda nafaqat ochlik glikemiyasi va HbA1c darajasini, balki ovqatdan keyingi giperglikemiya miqdorini ham hisobga olish kerak

2. HbA1c darajasining 7% yoki undan past bo'lgan qattiq nazorati, yoshi, jinsi, 2-toifa diabetning davomiyligi yoki HbA1c boshlang'ich darajasidan qat'i nazar, yurak-qon tomir o'limini oshirmasdan, yurak-qon tomir kasalliklari xavfini kamaytirishga yordam beradi

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ORGANIZATION OF MARKETING ACTIVITIES IN THE ENTERPRISE

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Annotatsiya: This article describes the skills, rules and perspectives of organizing marketing activities for small business enterprises.

Key words: theory of marketing activity, European society, economic cooperation, National Marketing Association, Market awareness, Spotify, Top marketing ranking.

Introduction. Marketing activity is an activity that consists of organizing and managing the production and sale of goods of the enterprise. The term "marketing activity" was introduced into use in the 60s of the 19th century by McCovern. Marketing as a theoretical concept and a unique phenomenon of commercial activity was first used in the USA at the beginning of the 20th century. High concentration of production and capital, dominance of monopolies in economic sectors, emergence of fierce competition in the international market objectively brought the problem of product sales to the fore. In 1908, the first specialized firm to study marketing problems appeared in the United States. In 1911, a number of large companies of the time opened their first commercial research departments. "Marketing" departments began to be established at companies, which deal with market research, advertising, customer service and other tasks of management. In 1931, the American Marketing Society was formed, and in 1937, the American National Marketing Association was formed. international marketing organizations such as the International Marketing Federation, the European Society for Public Opinion and Marketing and the European Marketing Academy were established. Marketing is one of the modern professions called marketing

Knowing the market (comprehensive study of consumers, knowing their tastes and desires), adapting to the market, influencing the market are the main principles of marketing. Also, a comprehensive study of issues related to the application of